

Identity Over Safety? How Social Solidarity and Cultural Identity Shape Resistance to Flood Relocation in Coastal Indonesia

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Abstract

Background: In Sayung Subdistrict, Demak, people's perception of flood risk is influenced by two main factors: government information about relocation and the strength of solidarity and cultural identity among residents. Residents are aware of the high risk, but feel unable or unprepared to relocate because they fear losing their identity and social connections. Therefore, social solidarity is a strong reason for them to refuse relocation.

Objective: To analyse social solidarity and cultural identity in relation to the interpretation of tidal flood risk information and attitudes towards relocation policies among coastal communities in Demak Regency, Indonesia.

Methodology: Qualitative research using interpretative phenomenology analysed residents' experiences and perceptions of tidal flooding risk communication. Data were collected through 60–90 minute semi-structured in-depth interviews, field observations, and literature reviews.

Results: This study demonstrates that strong social solidarity fosters resistance to relocation policies, as reflected in community cohesion, mutual assistance, and effective informal coordination. The community perceives their homes and the sea as ancestral heritage and tidal

flooding as destiny. As a result, the community has developed participatory disaster management adaptations.

Conclusion: Effective risk communication in coastal areas requires integrating cultural identity and social solidarity as primary channels for conveying mitigation messages.

Unique Contribution: This study confirms that cultural identity and social solidarity are forms of social capital that strengthen risk communication and the resilience of coastal communities. This is evidenced by collective adaptations such as road elevation, embankment construction, and mangrove planting, which demonstrate local capacity and community cooperation.

Key Recommendation: Central and local governments need to prioritise social solidarity and cultural identity in risk communication by utilising religious forums and traditional leaders, and by combining formal and cultural approaches to improve preparedness and acceptance of mitigation measures.

Keywords: Risk Communication; Social Solidarity; Culture; Coastal Communities; Disaster Mitigation

Introduction

In recent years, global trends have shown an increase in the frequency and intensity of tidal flooding due to climate change, rising sea levels, and land subsidence. (Masson et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2023). These changes have a significant impact on vulnerable regions, such as Southeast Asia and the Pacific, where large populations reside near coastlines that are experiencing rising sea levels. (Ashrafuzzaman et al., 2022). Thus, the implications for settlements and adaptation policies are urgent, necessitating an integrated approach to flood risk management that involves local communities, governments, and international institutions. (Clayton et al., 2023).

Tidal flooding and land subsidence in the northern coastal region of Java, including the Sayung subdistrict of Demak Regency, have had a significant impact on local communities. Research shows that this area has experienced land subsidence of up to 15 cm/year, which exacerbates the risk of tidal flooding due to a sea level rise of 6-10 mm per year. (Abidin et al., 2022). The impact of this phenomenon is evident in the damage to infrastructure and in the social and economic aspects, where communities must adapt to the loss of agricultural land. (Asrofi et al., 2024).

The risk communication and relocation policy in Indonesia reveals a top-down, technocratic government approach that is often at odds with the way local communities understand risk. (Muhajir, 2025). Research indicates that a narrative gap exists between the government's vision and the public's perception of risk, resulting in resistance to mitigation and relocation policies. It is recommended that communication strategies involve greater active participation from the community, draw on local knowledge, and ensure that the policies implemented align with the community's needs and social context. (Halim et al., 2024). This thereby increases confidence and effectiveness in disaster risk management. These conditions form the basis for this study.

Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

The RPA (Risk Perception Attitude) theory is a framework that describes the relationship between risk perception and self-efficacy. Self-efficacy acts as a moderator that enables individuals to translate risk perception into intent to act, supporting research that emphasises the importance of this factor in predicting behaviour. An example of the application of RPA in

disaster situations can be seen in the US state of Louisiana, where research shows a strong relationship between RPA and information efficacy when facing pluvial floods, demonstrating how individuals' perceptions can influence their response to disasters (Rainear & Lin, 2021). The strength of this model lies in its ability to explain important moderating variables when risk perception does not always trigger action; it serves to understand how uncertainty can influence efficacy and follow-through. However, its limitation lies in the variation of results depending on context, where the strength of efficacy and social norms can influence the accuracy of results.

In coastal areas of Indonesia, research on risk communication continues to reveal inconsistencies, particularly when viewed from a social and cultural perspective in the context of tidal flooding. (Aksa & Afrian, 2022). Most previous studies tend to employ quantitative, technocratic, and top-down approaches, often overlooking local values and community perspectives, despite the importance of both in accepting risk information. To overcome these limitations, the phenomenological approach is relevant because it captures both the subjective meaning of individuals and the local values inherent in risk perception, thereby enriching our understanding of how communities interpret and respond to disaster threats.

Previous studies have demonstrated the important role of socio-cultural communication in building the resilience of coastal communities to tidal flooding (Febriana et al., 2025). However, this focus has not yet extensively examined the dynamics of community responses to the relocation policy rolled out by the government. Therefore, this study broadens the analysis by highlighting the role of cultural identity and social solidarity rooted in coastal communities, which have proven to be key factors in shaping community attitudes towards relocation.

Methodologies

This study uses a qualitative approach with interpretive phenomenology to explore the factors that influence flood risk communication among coastal communities. This approach is based on Alfred Schutz's social phenomenology, which views reality as a social construct formed through daily interactions, historical experiences, and cultural contexts. Phenomenology was chosen because it can reveal how people's perceptions of risk, meanings, and responses to floods are determined not only by official information from the government, but also by social, economic, and cultural factors inherent in collective life (Englander & Morley, 2023). This approach is helpful because it helps researchers understand how social, economic, and cultural factors form risk perceptions in communal life, thus going beyond technocratic and quantitative approaches that often ignore community experiences.

This research was conducted in Sayung Subdistrict, Demak Regency. Informants were selected using purposive sampling, followed by snowball sampling to ensure the involvement of individuals with direct experience in communication and flood risk. Snowball sampling was used to reach key informants and ensure that the criteria were met, namely, direct experience with tidal flooding. Participants included those who had lived in the affected location for more than twenty years and were actively involved in mitigation efforts. A total of 10 informants were interviewed in depth, consisting of residents, community leaders, and village officials. Data analysis was conducted using an interpretative phenomenological approach based on updated frameworks in qualitative research. The analysis stages include verbatim transcription,

horizonisation to identify significant statements, and compiling textual descriptions, grouping meaning units into themes such as cultural identity, social solidarity, and adaptive responses. The results of the analysis are synthesised into a comprehensive narrative that reflects collective and individual experiences in a socio-cultural context. Data validity is tested through the member checking technique, in which Interviewees are asked to verify the accuracy of the interpretations compiled by the researcher (Beck, 2021).

Results and Discussion

In response to the increasingly frequent risk of tidal flooding, the government has proposed a relocation policy for residents in areas prone to tidal flooding. However, from the community's perspective, relocation is not merely a matter of moving house; it involves emotional attachments and the continuity of life that have been established over generations. This perspective can be explained through the *Risk Perception Attitude (RPA) Framework* developed by Rimal and Real (2003), which suggests that a combination of risk perception and self-efficacy greatly influences the community's response to risk. Communities that are aware of the high risk of flooding but feel they have no control or viable alternatives to act (low efficacy). In this context, residents choose to stay despite being aware of the threat of flooding because relocating is seen as a threat to their identity and social connections. Thus, the factors of social solidarity and cultural identity complement the RPA theory (Rimal & Real, 2003). The results of observations and interviews with informants in Sayung Subdistrict, Demak, Indonesia, were grouped based on the issues studied, namely:

Table 1: Respondent profile, cultural identity, social solidarity, and responses

Interviewee	Cultural Identity	Social Solidarity	Response
Interviewee 1	Living alongside the sea since childhood	Neighbours look after each other's homes and surroundings; the home is part of the community.	My house has been raised three times; even though the tidal floods keep coming, we remain steadfast.
Interviewee 2	Still maintaining the traditions passed down from parents	Helping neighbours during floods	The school has been raised so that the children can study more safely. That makes us confident to stay.
Interviewee 3	A house is not just a place to live. It is where we are born, raised, and raise our children. It holds memories.	Living on the coast reflects social solidarity through mutual support among residents.	The house has been raised three times.
Interviewee 4	Feeling that this land is part of the family heritage	Helping each other	The house is raised almost two metres above the ground.

Interviewee 5	Like family, it feels comfortable with weekly recitations and tahlilan.	Like family, it feels comfortable with weekly recitations and tahlilan.	Building embankments with sacks filled with soil
Interviewee 6	Has lived for decades	Participate in maintaining the mosque and social activities	We help each other raise the main road. That way, even if there is flooding, transport access can continue.
Interviewee 7	Since being born here, I have been taking care of my parents' meals	Helping each other when the tidal floods come	The school receives funding from the central government, so the children can study more calmly.
Interviewee 8	Continuing the fishing profession as a family identity since the grandfather's time	Frequently working together at sea and sharing the catch	We build embankments from sandbags and plant mangroves. That is how we protect our village.
Interviewee 9	Still believe in traditional knowledge as a guide for life	Participate in community service to clean the waterways	Start planting mangroves
Interviewee 10	Do not want to move because it is close to the sea.	Working together to pave the road reflects the social solidarity of the residents.	Residents helped each other raise the road with stones and soil.

Cultural Identity: Houses and the Sea as Ancestral Heritage

The coastal community's perception of tidal flooding is shaped by cultural factors, including local values and traditions that have been passed down from generation to generation. In the view of some residents, tidal flooding is not just a natural phenomenon, but part of God's will that must be accepted with open arms. This belief gives rise to an attitude of resignation, which does not necessarily mean giving up, but rather a form of obedience to a way of life that is considered normal. These cultural values frame the way communities interpret risk, where adaptation is not only technical but also spiritual.

I was born in this place, and my children were also raised here. This space is not merely a house, but a representation of our life and collective identity. The prospect of relocation raises profound concerns, particularly regarding the graves of my parents and the potential loss of long-standing bonds with neighbours who are regarded as family (Interviewee 7).

The dependence of coastal communities on maritime culture goes beyond its economic function as a source of livelihood. The fishing profession is viewed not only as a job but also as part of a way of life passed down from one generation to the next. The sea is a space for daily interaction, a workplace, and a spiritually meaningful place that is both respected and relied upon. For residents, the sea is not only a source of livelihood but also a symbol of identity and sustainability. Therefore, relocation is perceived as a double threat: firstly, it breaks the continuity of family identity and ancestral heritage attached to the house; and secondly, it separates the community from the sea, which is a symbol of their identity and livelihood.

Fishing is not just about catching fish. Here, it is a cultural identity. My grandfather was a fisherman, my father was too, and now I am. Seeing the sea early in the morning brings me peace. If I moved to a place without the sea, I think my life would feel empty (Interviewee 8).

In this context, perceptions of tidal flooding risk are influenced by inherent cultural values. Risk communication delivered by the government through a procedural approach often fails to address cultural dimensions that are important to citizens. Therefore, effective risk communication must bridge technical aspects with the cultural realities within society.

Table 2: Cultural identity factors that influence perception

Cultural Identity Factors	Explanation
The Existential Meaning of Home	Houses are considered part of one's identity and ancestral heritage, not just buildings. Relocation is seen as a threat to the continuity of family identity.
Cultural Dependence on the Sea	The fishing profession is not only an economic activity, but also a part of the coastal way of life and culture. The sea has symbolic and existential value for coastal residents.

Source: researcher data analysis

Social Solidarity as Resistance to Relocation

The perception of coastal communities regarding the social factors related to tidal flooding is shaped by intense social interaction and strong collective values within the community. Tidal flooding is not always perceived as a disaster, but is often considered a natural part of the cycle of life that must be faced together. Solidarity among residents, mutual assistance, and emotional attachment to the living environment strengthen their social bonds in responding to risks. Information about flooding is often disseminated through informal channels, such as conversations between neighbours, community leaders, or announcements at mosques, which are considered more credible and relevant than government information. These findings indicate that the government has failed to fulfil the principle of "be first, be right, be credible" as emphasised in the CERC model, because the technocratic top-down approach often clashes with the reality of people's experiences.

Neighbours help each other look after their homes and the environment, because for us, our homes are also part of our community and shared memories (Interviewee 1).

Social cohesion and community solidarity in coastal communities are reflected in close social relationships and ongoing collective activities, such as religious recitations, tahlilan (prayer gatherings), community service, and religious celebrations. These activities are not only a means of interaction, but also a medium for strengthening the values of togetherness, a sense of belonging, and a deep communal identity. The emotional bonds formed from this

togetherness make it difficult for the community to leave their environment, even though the threat of tidal flooding is increasing and the government is offering relocation options. Social bonds formed through religious practices and collective work reduce the acceptability of relocation, as residents perceive it as a threat to their daily support networks and the stability of communal life.

Here, we are like family and feel comfortable. Every week, there are religious lectures and tahlilan, so we often gather and help each other. If we move, we are afraid of losing this family atmosphere, because it is not certain that we will be as close in the new place (Interviewee 5).

For residents, housing is not just about a place to live, but also about access to the livelihoods that have sustained them. When risk communication comes in the form of a relocation appeal, many perceive it as a threat to the stability of the lives they have fought for. Risk is assessed not only in terms of potential physical danger but also in terms of the possibility of severed social ties. Therefore, risk communication not based on experiential dimensions is not accepted, as it clashes with the reality the community has come to understand.

Table 3: Social solidarity factors influencing perception

The Factor of Social Solidarity	Explanation
Social Engagement and Community Solidarity	The community is involved in close social relationships, such as religious gatherings, tahlilan (prayer gatherings), and community service, which foster a sense of belonging.
Access to information sources	The community responds more to neighbours' conversations and mosque announcements than to formal information, which is why risk communication is understood as a dialogical process.

Source: research data analysis

Participatory Adaptation and Community Capacity

The adaptation efforts undertaken by coastal communities reflect how they interpret and respond to the risk of tidal flooding, which is part of their daily lives. Perceptions of risk play an important role in driving adaptive actions, both individually and collectively. The greater the community's awareness of the dangers of tidal flooding, the greater the impetus to take protective and adaptive measures.

I have raised my house three times. If I had not, every time there was a flood, water would have entered the house. Now I am still saving little by little to raise it again (Interviewee 3)

The floor of this house used to be level with the ground. However, because water was coming in more often, we gradually raised it. Now it is almost two metres above the ground. We did it all ourselves. We did not expect any help (Interviewee 4).

This statement reflects that raising houses is not only a form of adaptation to physical risks but also a survival strategy in the context of uncertainty. Adaptation is carried out independently, despite the heavy economic consequences, such as borrowing money or selling assets. In addition to houses, public facilities such as schools are also built. This process is often carried

out through community cooperation and supported by external contributions, such as those from NGOs or central government programmes proposed by the village government.

The school was often flooded, and the children had to move around while studying. Now that it has been raised, they can study in a more peaceful environment. This effort is proof that even though we live in limited circumstances, we continue to fight for the future of our children (Interviewee 7).

Collective action by the community demonstrates strong local adaptive capacity, not resignation. Participatory adaptation involves raising houses and roads, building embankments, planting mangroves, and managing floodgates. These are survival strategies born of collective awareness and supported by internal risk communication that encourages community cooperation. Through this mechanism, the community demonstrates its commitment to maintaining social, economic, and educational connectivity amid the threat of tidal flooding.

The collective raising of roads is one important adaptation measure taken by communities in response to increasingly frequent tidal flooding. Roads submerged by seawater not only hinder daily activities but also pose a threat to the safety of residents.

When the children had difficulty going to school because the water on the road was knee-high, we finally worked together to buy stones and soil to fill the road. We worked every afternoon to raise the road, because for us, the road is a significant main access point (Interviewee 10)

Access to proper roads is a basic necessity for coastal communities. Safe roads facilitate work, school, and worship, while also ensuring continuity of life amid daily flooding. When roads are flooded, mobility comes to a halt. Therefore, residents raise the roads through cooperation as a form of adaptation and commitment to maintaining social, economic, and educational connectivity, ensuring that life can continue amid tidal flooding.

The community built emergency embankments from available materials, such as sacks filled with soil and concrete, and installed simple floodgates at strategic points to regulate the flow. At high tide, residents closed the floodgates to prevent seawater intrusion. At low tide, they opened them to drain the floodwaters. These activities were carried out in shifts by the residents.

We build embankments with sacks filled with soil to prevent water from entering the village. If any of them break, we repair them together. We guard these floodgates together. When the tide is high, we close them. When the river recedes, we open them so the water can flow out (Interviewee 5).

Mangrove planting along the coastline is one way in which communities are adapting to the increasingly frequent risks of abrasion and tidal flooding. This activity has been carried out, especially after abrasion eroded most of the coastal area. Residents work together to plant mangrove seedlings along the coastline that borders their settlements. The aim is to create a natural barrier that can reduce the force of the waves before they reach the land.

Now we have started planting mangroves. There used to be many mangroves, but they have since disappeared due to erosion. They are important for holding back the waves and high tide. Without mangroves, the water could flood straight into the village (Interviewee 9).

This mangrove planting activity is an example of how communities use natural methods to protect themselves from disasters. Mangroves not only protect against waves, but also bring many benefits to nature and daily life. This effort shows that communities are aware of the importance of maintaining a safer and more sustainable environment.

Table 4: Adaptation of coastal communities

Types of Adaptation	Public Response
House Elevation	Done independently according to economic means. Some houses have been raised three times.
School Elevation	The school was elevated through central funds proposed by the village government.
Road Elevation	The main road was built through cooperation, as it serves as the main transportation access.
Construction of Embankments and Sluice Gates	Constructing embankments from sacks filled with soil and manual sluice gates to open and close the channels.
Mangrove Planting	Carried out collectively to withstand waves and prevent abrasion.

Source: Researcher data analysis

Risk is understood as a social construct that involves more than just technical probability, but is influenced by cultural context, individual experience, social norms, and collective values. In RPA, the principle of "be first, be right, be credible" is crucial for building trust and credibility of the message source, which is a key factor in successful risk communication (Guedalia et al., 2024). In the context of coastal communities in Indonesia, which have strong social and cultural solidarity, communication that fails to consider social and cultural adaptation tends to be ineffective (Bolton et al., 2022). Therefore, it is important to consider cultural and social values when designing risk communication strategies to ensure more effective and positive communication during emergencies.

This suggests that social solidarity and cultural identity serve as mediating variables, connecting risk messages with community responses. These variables guide individuals in interpreting information within pre-established cultural frameworks (Sasongko et al., 2025). In the context of coastal communities, traditional values in disaster response are evident in practices that maintain ecological relationships with the sea, which are integral to their cultural identity. A more responsive approach to local values and informal communication patterns, facilitated through community leaders, can enhance the effectiveness of risk communication and strengthen disaster resilience in high-risk communities (Abella & Salapa, 2024).

Research Limitations

This study focuses on a specific coastal community in Sayung District, Indonesia, using a qualitative phenomenological approach. This approach enables a deep understanding of cultural identity, social solidarity, and the dynamics of flood risk communication; however, the phenomenological nature limits the generalisation of findings to other coastal communities. The socio-economic, cultural, and geographical conditions of the Sayung coastal community are unique. The coping strategies and forms of risk communication identified may not be replicable in other coastal areas with different characteristics.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study demonstrates that social solidarity has a significant impact on coastal communities' perceptions of tidal flooding and relocation. Collective activities, such as religious gatherings and community service, foster a sense of togetherness, while access to livelihoods encourages residents to remain in vulnerable areas. Based on the RPA framework, communities perceive a high risk of flooding but have low self-efficacy regarding relocation due to concerns about losing social ties and economic stability. This makes solidarity a key factor in risk response. The community views relocation not merely as a change of residence but as a threat to cultural identity and life stability. Therefore, the choice to stay is perceived as safer, even though the threat of flooding is acknowledged. It is this combination of high risk perception and low relocation efficacy that underlies resistance to relocation.

Cultural identity shapes how coastal communities perceive risks and choose survival strategies. Tidal flooding is often viewed as part of life or as a manifestation of God's will, adapting not only physically but also spiritually and culturally. Reliance on the sea as a livelihood and identity strengthens resistance to relocation. Passed-down cultural frameworks guide risk interpretation, making top-down government communication often ineffective. In contrast, informal channels, such as those through local leaders and religious forums, are more trusted and relevant.

Community adaptation measures, such as elevating houses, schools, and roads, building embankments and floodgates, and planting mangroves, demonstrate a strong local capacity to face recurring risks. Cooperation in these activities also functions as internal risk communication, reinforcing solidarity and shared awareness. By applying the be first, be right, be credible principles of the CERC model and designing participatory strategies that integrate technical approaches with social solidarity and cultural identity, community resilience and sustainability can be maintained amid growing environmental challenges.

This study examines specific coastal communities affected by tidal flooding. Further research should specifically examine whether the mediating role of social solidarity and cultural identity remains a key factor in flood risk communication and relocation resistance in other coastal areas with different socio-economic, cultural, and geographical characteristics.

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